

Studies on an Electrochemical Cell : Cu/CuCl/Pt

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An electrochemical cell made up of CuCl pellet with copper and platinum disc electrodes has been studied. The maximum current available is about $800 \mu\text{A}$ in presence of a few milli moles of water. The charge transport in CuCl through positive holes diffusion due to concentration gradient has been suggested which is favoured by the solution of a quadratic equation of positive holes diffusion.

THE assembly of cuprous chloride pellet having the electrode configuration : Cu/CuCl/Pt was first used by Wagner and Wagner¹ for estimating the fraction of positive hole conductivity in CuCl in the temperature range of 250 to 400°. The working principle of the electrode configuration as envisaged by Wagner *et al* was, that after applying a positive E.M.F. to the Pt electrode (applied potential less than decomposition potential of CuCl) all interstitials, cuprous ions would be diffused from Pt side of pellet towards the copper electrode and under steady state condition when all Cu^+ are exhausted the current is exclusively carried by positive holes. Harrison and Prasad^{2,3} later used this electrode configuration for the determination of electronic-ionic transition in CuCl in the temperature range of 24° to 240° where some part of the results below 130° were ambiguous. While attempting to observe this ambiguity, Prasad and Srivastava⁴ (this work) observed that at room temperature even without applying any E.M.F. this electrode assembly produces current of the order of microamps and this current increase many fold in presence of moisture as described here.

Experimental

Cuprous chloride (A.R., B.D.H.) was dissolved in 6M HCl and CuCl was precipitated in distilled water. White precipitate of CuCl was washed with acetone and absolute alcohol. Solid mass was filtered, dried in vacuum and stored in vacuum desiccator for further use. Pellets were prepared from 1.5 gm of material at a pressure of 750 lbs for three minutes in a Punch and Die model 341-20 (N. J., U.S.A.). The diameter of pellet was 13 mm and thickness was 2 mm. Pellet was sandwiched between a bright weighed copper and Pt disc electrodes. The contact was ensured by an external spring. Low short circuit current of the cell was measured with the help of a microammeter model No. 474 (KYCEE) and the higher current with the help of an ammeter model 301 Weston. The E.M.F. of the cell was measured with the help of Avometer

TFMI (APLAB) and H. P. Electrometer and AC resistance at 10 0 cps with Beckman Conductivity meter model RC-18 A.

Results and Discussion

First of all the measurements were made in absence of moisture and thereafter the cell was brought in contact with moisture. Pellet of CuCl sandwiched between copper and platinum disc electrodes acts itself as a cell with copper as a negative and platinum as a positive electrode, giving a current of the order of a microamps. Though the short circuit current was measured the results have been described in terms of current density. The current density in absence of moisture was $\sim 1.0 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ which remained constant for hours. Some variable E.M.F. from 0.46 volt to 0.75 volt were observed. However, most samples gave an E.M.F. of 0.75 volt and therefore this value is taken for discussion. The specific resistance of the cell was $\sim 4.50 \times 10^8 \text{ ohm cm}$. These parameters of the cell were reproducible for each cell made from different pellets within 5%.

The result in presence of moisture were drastically different. The current density begins to rise at the rate of $4.4 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ as soon as the moisture comes in contact with CuCl pellet. The current density, E.M.F. and resistance measured after 20 minutes of moisture absorption were found to be $90 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, 0.46 volt and $5 \times 10^8 \text{ ohms cm}$ respectively. This trend of increase of current density continued approximately for three hours giving a maximum value of $800 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. Under this condition the E.M.F. of the cell and resistance were found to be 0.11 volt and 950 ohms cm respectively. Further increase in the current was not observed rather this value remained stationary for three hours. The aforesaid behaviour of current and time has been shown in Fig. 1. This behaviour was found to be reasonably reproducible from cell to cell made from different pellets. Further measurements that is after six hours were terminated

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Fig. 1.

since pellet becomes relatively more moist and therefore the data up to three hours only have been taken for discussion.

The history of pellet seems to play some significant role in the system since it was observed that the E.M.F. and the resistance of the cell were not reproducible on used pellets. Other noticeable change was the adherence of cupric chloride (bluish compound) on the open surface of pellet. A film of white cuprous chloride was also observed on Pt electrode. There was a weight loss in copper electrode but only less than 0.1% of the lost copper was found to be deposited on the platinum electrode. This was determined in a separate experiment continued for three weeks.

For the interpretation of the results described above it is necessary to know what would be the driving force which could sustain the current of the cell. The data of current density and E.M.F. obtained in the absence of moisture indicate that some kind of solid state electrode reactions are taking place. It is, therefore, suggested that the probable electrode reaction could be :

This cell reaction would correspond to a change in free energy of -74KJ which should give an E.M.F. of 0.767 volt. Such an E.M.F. across a high impedance cell ($\sim 10^5$ ohms) should correspond to an ohmic current of a few microamps. The observed values of E.M.F. and current density are 0.75 volt and $1.20 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ respectively. Such a close agreement between the expected and observed values shows that the cell appears to behave as a pseudo galvanic cell under moisture free condition with only difference that cell material as a high impedance p-type semiconductor.

Now as soon as the cell comes in contact with the moisture the situation changes. Enormous rise in the current density at the rate of $4 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{min}^{-1}$ up to $800 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ and decrease of E.M.F. from 0.75 volt down to 0.11 volt clearly show that the electrode reactions referred above are greatly influenced by the presence of moisture. We believe

that in presence of moisture the oxidation of cuprous chloride to cupric state is favoured as per this stoichiometry.

This oxidation has two main effects from the charge transport standpoint (i) it sets free the electrons of Cu^+ and (ii) it increases the concentration of positive holes in CuCl .

The increase in the concentration of positive holes in CuCl may be visualized from the following arguments. The valence band structure of cuprous chloride is of mixed character⁵ in which the contribution of wave function of Cu-3d orbitals and Cl-3p orbitals are about 80% and 20% respectively. Foreign anions absorbed by CuCl combines with the electrons of Cu-3d making Cu^+ as if Cu^{++} exists in CuCl lattice (Zn S). This deficiency of Cu-3d electrons caused by foreign anions amounts a positive hole in the valence band and it would behave as a positive charge carrier as long as Cu^{++} remains a part of CuCl .

If this is true then as a result of this oxidation of CuCl by moisture, eventually all Cu^+ after becoming Cu^{++} should tend to form its own lattice. But since copper is in contact with CuCl pellet, this tendency of Cu^{++} would be minimised. In other words, deficiency of Cu^+ in CuCl created by Cu^{++} is compensated by oxidation of Cu , i.e. $\text{Cu} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^+ + e$. This tends to maintain CuCl close to original stoichiometry. Thus a chain type of oxidation that is $\text{Cu} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^+ \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{++}$ sets in. The reduction of Cu^{++} to Cu^+ as mentioned in equation (2) at the Pt electrode does not possibly compete with the oxidation at the copper electrode. Thus the net effect of oxidation of CuCl by moisture is the enormous increase electrons and positive holes over their concentration already existed in CuCl before the reaction. The approximate concentration of positive holes in CuCl at 20° before the reaction with moisture estimated from current density data is $\sim 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and to satisfy the current density data in moist condition the hole concentration should be of the order of 10^{19} cm^{-3} . In these approximations the mobility of positive holes has been assumed to be $\sim 0.10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ volt}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Thus the electrons released and accumulated at the copper electrode are pushed through the external wire whereas the building up of a large concentration gradient of positive holes in CuCl perhaps acts as a driving force for transporting the positive charge through CuCl pellet and this flow of electrons and holes through external wire and pellet respectively appears to be probable cause to sustain the short circuit current in the cell.

The argument of electronic current due to concentration gradient of positive holes is further supported by the following mathematical deduction.

The diffusion of positive holes due to the concentration gradient may be written in this form⁶

$$J = -D \left(\frac{dh}{dx} \right) - \mu h \left(\frac{dE}{dx} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

where J = positive hole current, D, μ , h and dh/dx and dE/dx are diffusion coefficient, mobility, concentration, concentration gradient of positive holes and electric potential gradient respectively. Substituting the values of these parameters that is

$$D = (kT/e)\mu \text{ and } De \frac{dE}{dx} = -\mu \frac{kT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx} \text{ in equation (1)}$$

(where σ is the positive hole conductivity) the above equation can be transformed into quadratic form of μ that is

$$\left(\frac{hkT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx} \right) \mu^2 - \left(\frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \right) \mu - J = 0 \quad \dots (2)$$

This equation is based on the assumption that positive hole current supersedes the ionic current and the net current results from the accumulation and diffusion of positive holes in CuCl. The solution of equation (2) is

$$\mu = \frac{\left(\frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \pm \right) \left\{ \left(\frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \right)^2 + \frac{4hkT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx} J \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\frac{2hkT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx}} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{or } \mu = \frac{\frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \pm \left(\frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \right) \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{4hkT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx} J / \left(\frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}}{\frac{2hkT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx}} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{or } \mu = \frac{1}{\frac{2hkT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx}} \frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \pm \frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \left\{ 1 + \frac{4hJe^2}{\sigma kT \frac{dh}{dx}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (5)$$

Expanding the terms under square root of equation

(5) and after neglecting the smaller terms it becomes

$$\mu = \left\{ \frac{kT}{e} \frac{dk}{dx} \pm \frac{kT}{e} \frac{dh}{dx} \left(1 + \frac{2hJe^2}{\sigma kT \frac{dh}{dx}} \right) \right\} \left(\frac{2hkT}{\sigma} \frac{dh}{dx} \right)^{-1} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\text{or } \mu = \frac{\sigma}{he} + \frac{Je}{kT \frac{dh}{dx}} \quad \dots (7)$$

Substituting the value of $\sigma = eh\mu$ in equation (7) one can write

$$\mu = \mu + \frac{Je}{kT \frac{dh}{dx}} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{Je}{kT} \left(\frac{dh}{dx} \right)^{-1} = 0 \quad \dots (9)$$

Equation (9) predicts that $\frac{dh}{dx}^{-1} \equiv 0$ since e, kT

are constants and J is the experimentally observed quantity. Thus some finite current will be observed only if a large concentration gradient exist in the system.

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